

METHODOLOGY FOR VIRTUAL TEACHING DIFFICULT PROBLEMS IN MATHEMATICS (BASED ON THE EXAMPLE OF ADDING AND SUBTRACTING MIXED FRACTIONS)

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Annotation: Methods of virtual teaching of difficult-to-master mathematics problems are implemented in different ways. Fractions are also a very big topic in mathematics, including mixed fractions. It is important to be able to explain to children and teach them simple ways to solve examples.

Key words: improper fractions, addition of mixed fractions, subtraction of mixed fractions, addition of mixed fractions.

We know that in mathematics the topic of Fractions is one of the fundamental and main topics of the course, on which the algebra of calculating fractions with variables is further based, the laws of short multiplication, etc. are used. At the beginning we go through addition and subtraction of fractions with like denominators, and then we go through addition and subtraction of fractions with different denominators, and here we need to build on the topics of finding the common multiple of numbers GCM, GCD. It is necessary to find the common denominator of fractions; this is where students have difficulties in mastering them. Let's think about adding mixed fractions. Wow is this supposed to happen? All their parts are added separately and the result is written to the right of the equal sign;

Then the fractional parts are added, if an improper fraction is formed, then its whole part is separated and added to the resulting whole part, and the remaining fraction is written down, if a fraction that can be reduced is formed, then it is reduced.

For example,

$$1 \text{ Example. } 1\frac{13}{10} + 2\frac{9}{10} = \frac{(13+29)}{10} = \frac{42}{10} = 4.2 = 4\frac{1}{5}$$

$$2 \text{ Example. } 1\frac{3}{10} + 2\frac{9}{10} = 3\frac{(3+9)}{10} = 3\frac{12}{10} = 4\frac{2}{10} = 4\frac{1}{5}$$

To divide mixed fractions you need to:

Divide all their parts and write the difference to the right of the equal sign;

If a fraction is formed by dividing parts of a fraction, then it is reduced and added to the whole part.

$$\text{Or } 3\frac{2}{4} = \frac{3 \cdot 4 + 2}{4} = \frac{14}{4}$$

There are two ways to add a mixed fraction:

Calculating mixed fractions as improper fractions;

$$2\frac{3}{4} + 1\frac{1}{4} = \frac{11}{4} + \frac{5}{4} = \frac{(11 + 5)}{4} = \frac{16}{4} = 4$$

In this method, an integer is added to a whole number, and a fraction is added to a fraction.

$$2\frac{3}{4} + 1\frac{1}{4} = 3\frac{4}{4} = 3 + 1 = 4$$

What should you do if the denominators are different when adding and subtracting mixed fractions?

Let's look at how to calculate a mixed fraction with different denominators. We use the upper formula, calculate only the integer parts separately, and then the fractional ones separately, write down the resulting integer part at the beginning, and then the fractional one.

For example:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{74}{5} + 4\frac{2}{3} &= \frac{74}{5} + \frac{4 \cdot 3 + 2}{3} = \frac{74}{5} + \frac{14}{3} = \frac{(\frac{15}{5} \cdot 74)}{15} + \frac{(\frac{15}{3} \cdot 14)}{15} = \frac{3 \cdot 74}{15} + \frac{5 \cdot 14}{15} \\ &= \frac{144}{15} + \frac{70}{15} = \frac{214}{15} = 14\frac{4}{15} \end{aligned}$$

When calculating this fraction, we can first convert it to an improper fraction;

$$\frac{39}{5} + \frac{14}{3}$$

Now, if we give a common denominator, we would separate the largest denominator and divide it by the smallest denominator, but we know that this method is not correct, that is, 5 cannot be divided by 3. If we give 10, this is also not correct, we get 15. If we divide 15 by 3, we get 5 without a remainder. The common denominator will be 15.

Now if we divide 15 by 5 we get 3, multiply the image by 3: $39 \cdot 3 = 117$

If we divide 15 by 3 we get 5 and use this method again: $14 \cdot 5 = 70$

$$\frac{(117 + 70)}{15} = \frac{187}{15}$$

Didactic game for consolidation:

Give 4 pears equally to 3 children. We divide 4 pears by 3, i.e. we bring them to an improper fraction.

$$\frac{4}{3} = 1 + \frac{1}{3} = 1\frac{1}{3}$$

this means 1 whole pear and 1 third of a pear.

If a book of 205 pages is read in 4 days, let's calculate how many pages can be read in a day.

$$\frac{205}{4} = \frac{204}{4} + \frac{1}{4} = 51 + \frac{1}{4} = 51\frac{1}{4}$$

In this case, 51 pages of a book are read in one day and the last 1 page remains unread.

Using virtuality in reinforcement:

When using virtuality, it is important that the reader understands the topic. In this case, we will highlight the letters on the screen in the “Surat-Numerator” and “Mahraj-Denominator” cells. The numbers appear on the decimal line and denominator. This example represents an improper fraction. The student converts an improper fraction to a mixed fraction and performs the calculations. Figure 1. Form 1.

A	B	D	E	F
G	H	I	J	K
L	M	N	O	P
Q	R	S	T	U
V	X	Y	Z	W

Denominator

A	B	D	E	F
G	H	I	J	K
L	M	N	O	P
Q	R	S	T	U
V	X	Y	Z	W

Figure 2. Form 2.

13	19	26	43	35
29	19	23	57	62
31	57	23	43	41

41	68	46	53	34
53	67	71	17	61

Denominator

5	7	5	9	7
8	6	3	9	5
7	4	7	6	3
9	8	3	5	4
2	7	9	3	3

$$\text{For example: } \frac{L}{M} + \frac{N}{U} = \frac{31}{4} + \frac{23}{4} = 7\frac{3}{4} + 4\frac{3}{4} = 13\frac{1}{4}$$

$$\frac{G}{J} - \frac{K}{Y} = \frac{29}{9} - \frac{62}{9} = 3\frac{2}{9} - 6\frac{8}{9} = -3\frac{2}{3}$$

$$\frac{S}{F} - \frac{T}{J} = \frac{46}{7} - \frac{53}{9} = 6\frac{4}{7} - 5\frac{8}{9} = 6\frac{43}{63}$$

In conclusion, I can say that the topic of fractions is a very big topic. Learning is very difficult, you need a clear plan and time.. If the teacher cannot explain and present the essence, then it is not easy. It is a mistake to say that fractions are only needed in school. Let's give an example. Students also use fractions when necessary. If everything initially is not clear, this will cause many problems, i.e. if a student, while solving a complex example, made a mistake at the beginning, then of course the result will not be correct. This is not only due to fractions, but also to the wonderful examples that are processed using them. Now and in the future, it is necessary to be able to explain each topic correctly and diligently so that such problems do not arise in children.

It is necessary to study the psychology of children, to know to what extent they can accept knowledge of addition and subtraction of mixed fractions, and accordingly use different methods and techniques, different technologies. In order for children to understand, the teacher must be able to invent and implement various didactic games. When playing didactic games, it is necessary to explain to children the content and theme of the game and increase their interest.

And the use of virtuality in reinforcement is based on a perfect and clear basis. What interests students most? What should virtuality look like? Can the shape of numbers attract attention?

Based on these speculations, we decided to create a virtual game that can answer the above questions. It will help consolidate students' knowledge on this topic.

References:

1. Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarining 6-sinf uchun darslik. Toshkent-2017
2. FRUsmonov, RDI somov, BOXo'jayev “Matematikadan qo'llanma” Toshkent <<Yangi asr avlodi>> 2006.
3. Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarining 5- sinfi uchun darslik. Toshkent-2015
4. <https://arxiv.uz/uz/documents/slaydlar/algebra/aralash-sonlar-qo-shish-va-ayirish-dars-ishlanma>
5. <https://talim.uz/uz/subject/matematika-uz/6-sinf/aralash-kasrlarni-qoshish-va-ayirish-1-dars>